

ENGINEERING INFORMATION SYSTEMS:
IMPLEMENTATION APPROACHES AND ISSUES

Anthony J. Gadiant
Captain, USAF

VHSIC Program Office
Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio 45433

ABSTRACT

The phenomenal growth in integrated circuit fabrication technology over the last decade has led to the need for a robust, multi-user, integrated design environment for electronic systems. Attempts to develop "integrated" design environments have highlighted the present lack in design tool interoperability. The Very High Speed Integrated Circuits (VHSIC) Program has recognized the importance of integrated design environments for the design of future defense electronic systems and for the insertion of new technologies into existing electronic systems. The VHSIC Program is attempting to ease the task of integrating disparate electronic system design aids by addressing the design tool interoperability problem through the Engineering Information System (EIS) Program. This panel is the second in a series of panels aimed at discussing different aspects of Engineering Information Systems. The first EIS panel, held at SIGMOD '86¹, discussed the major issues confronting the implementation of an EIS. The purpose of this panel is to discuss different implementation approaches that will address these issues.

INTRODUCTION

The Very High Speed Integrated Circuits (VHSIC) Program has developed an integrated circuit capability which can significantly increase the performance of defense electronic systems. (An electronic system is defined as a combination of both hardware and software). In order to economically realize this capability, the Department of Defense (DoD) must be able to efficiently design and insert VHSIC technology into new and existing electronic defense systems. This goal will require the development of an integrated design environment that supports the design, documentation, and life-cycle maintenance of complex electronic systems from the initial system specification through fabrication and test to maintenance. A design system with this degree of functionality is not available commercially because the development of such a large and complex "turn-key" system would require more

resources than any one business can afford. As a result, organizations which use Design Automation (DA) tools are forced to integrate an assorted set of design aids developed either internally or by different vendors. The integration task is complicated by the multi-user, distributed, heterogeneous design environment, and by the unique, proprietary, internal data representation of each vendor's design system. The objective of the Engineering Information System (EIS) Program is to reduce the present difficulties involved with integrating different vendors' design tools by developing a candidate set of "interoperability" standards.

ISSUES

The primary goal of an Engineering Information System is to provide a framework for the integration of engineering processes through computer aided engineering. An engineering process consists of the conceptualization, design, development, test, verification, fabrication, and maintenance of products for which form, fit and function is controlled. The key concept in this framework is the management of the complex and continuously evolving databases consisting of data objects associated with these engineering processes, and the integration of DA tools with database technology will be the foundation of it. In order to accomplish the above goal an EIS must possess the following functional characteristics.

First, an EIS must support reuse of previous designs. Most new products are permutations of past products, with new features or re-designed in a new technology. Leveraging off of existing designs can result in tremendous time and cost savings by creating a "Design Learning Curve" analogous to the learning curves seen in manufacturing. Reuse is also necessary to facilitate technological evolution through technology transfer. Presently "reuse" of design information is limited to small groups of people familiar with a given product line or technology. Technology transfer among different groups is so time consuming that it cannot catch-up with its own evolution.

In effect, by the time a technology is transferred from one group to another the technology being transferred is out of date. In order to make reuse possible, an EIS must provide a means for querying the database about existing designs. It must support hierarchical design methodologies where a design at one level can be composed of both new and previously-designed components at the next level. For the efficient and effective reuse of design information, an EIS must provide a design "audit trail." Because design is a series of tradeoffs, the design audit trail must capture the reasoning behind each tradeoff. Finally, in order to support reuse over a long period of time, an EIS must support a dynamic information model which can acquire new information as technologies change and which can link new versions of meta-data together with older versions.

Second, an EIS must support design in a distributed heterogeneous environment where different vendors' hardware platforms and databases might exist. The user must be presented with a virtual, logically centralized view of the design information. Virtual access by the user to the assortment of DA programs existing in the integrated design environment must also be supported. In addition, an EIS must provide substantial data management capabilities in this distributed environment; including, support for long transactions, and robust management and control mechanisms which allow organizations to develop individualized policies for ensuring the consistency of the design information across levels of design abstraction and between different design representations.

Third, an EIS must economically support the integration of existing software applications as well as future software applications. There must be adequate incentives for the CAE tool vendors to tailor their products for EIS environments. As a result, a revolutionary approach is not likely to succeed. An evolutionary approach in which the system is built in stages and where the user community has had the opportunity to affect the definition of the system is necessary.

Fourth, an EIS must be flexible. It must allow different users to tailor the system to their special needs based upon the set of software tools in their environment, and their particular design methodology. As a result, the system must be programmable. In effect, it must support a set of mechanisms that each organization can use to develop different, unique policies for such things as the management and control of the design information. In addition, an EIS must be extensible. Because the technology is dynamic an EIS must support the insertion and deletion of design tools, and a dynamic information model.

Finally, an EIS must provide all of the above functionality in an efficient manner because it must meet the performance requirements of potential users.

EIS PROGRAM

The EIS Program is a very important standardization effort for the VHSIC Program that has the potential to serve the industry, government, and academic communities as well. Once designed, the EIS will act to facilitate the rapid insertion of VHSIC technology into electronic systems by providing a framework for the integration CAE tools while simultaneously providing the Design Automation community with a candidate set of "interoperability" standards. The rationale behind, requirements for, and other aspects of the EIS Program are described in a variety of papers and documents^{2,3,4,5}.

EIS Program Organization

The Engineering Information System Program is organized into three phases. Phase I is comprised of the specification, documentation and delivery of a preliminary set of EIS specifications based upon potential user requirements. The first phase will last twelve months from the contract award date, Phase II and Phase III will last a combined total of 22 months, and will consist of the implementation (Phase II), and demonstration (Phase III) of the information management system and the interface specifications.

The initial specifications from Phase I will be evaluated by industry, academia and the Government in order to determine their adequacy. User participation in this process is particularly important for the reasons alluded to earlier. After the completion of Phase I, the evaluation process will be aided by a seminar and workshop in which the salient features of the specifications will be summarized and reviewed.

Following the evaluation process, Phase II will begin. The second phase of the Program will involve the specification, documentation, development and delivery of the final set of EIS specifications, and the development of the prototype software necessary to support them. The EIS prototype will then be demonstrated for evaluation by the user community and Government during Phase III.

At the completion of this effort, the user community will have a set of candidate standards which will have the potential to greatly increase existing and future design tool interoperability.

PANEL PARTICIPANTS

There has been a great deal of interest in the EIS Program which motivated the organization of this panel discussion. The EIS

Program is pleased to have the following panel participants:

Randy Katz, University of California, Berkeley
Mary Loomis, GE/Calma Company
Raymond Lorie, IBM Research
Darryl Olson, Boeing Computer Services
Alice Parker, University of Southern California
Katie Rotzell, MCC
Nick Roussopoulos, University of Maryland
Gio Wiederhold, Stanford University

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